

Interpretable symbolic regression for cosmological parameter recovery from CMB power spectra

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Abstract

Interpretable machine-learning methods provide a complementary approach to cosmological parameter inference by yielding explicit analytic relations between observables and model parameters. We investigate symbolic regression as an interpretable framework for recovering cosmological parameters from cosmic microwave background (CMB) power spectra in a controlled synthetic setting. Synthetic TT , TE , and EE angular power spectra are generated using CAMB across a five-parameter Λ CDM-inspired parameter space, and symbolic regression models are trained to recover n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_b , ω_{cdm} , and τ . Predictive performance is evaluated using held-out test data together with robustness and uncertainty analyses, and comparisons are made against Random Forest and multilayer perceptron (MLP) baselines. Symbolic regression recovers n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ with high accuracy ($R^2 \gtrsim 0.99$), yielding compact analytic expressions that capture physically plausible spectral sensitivities. Perturbation and feature-ablation analyses recover qualitatively expected parameter sensitivities, including the importance of low- ℓ polarization information for τ and higher- ℓ structure for n_s . Robustness tests show stable performance under controlled perturbations and re-sampling variations. In contrast, ω_b is substantially more difficult to infer directly from raw spectra, but feature engineering based on acoustic peak morphology significantly improves recovery and produces compact interpretable relations. These results indicate a parameter-dependent pattern in the symbolic recoverability of cosmological information from CMB spectra and suggest that symbolic regression, particularly when combined with physics-informed feature design, provides a complementary interpretable surrogate-modeling framework for constructing compact mappings between CMB observables and cosmological parameters in controlled synthetic settings.

Keywords: cosmic microwave background, cosmological parameters, symbolic regression, interpretable machine learning, surrogate modeling, computational cosmology

1. Introduction

The cosmic microwave background (CMB) remains one of the primary probes of precision cosmology. Measurements of its temperature and polarization anisotropies have enabled tight constraints on the parameters of the standard cosmological model, culminating in the Planck 2018 analysis presented by Aghanim et al. (2020), which established the now-standard six-parameter Λ CDM framework with high precision. In practice, cosmological parameter inference relies on accurate forward modeling of CMB observables using Boltzmann solvers such as CAMB (Lewis et al., 2000) and CLASS (Lesgourgues, 2011), together with likelihood-based statistical pipelines.

Machine learning has increasingly been explored as a complementary tool for cosmological inference. Neural-network approaches have been used to accelerate parameter estimation, as demonstrated by Auld et al. (2008), infer cosmological parameters directly from CMB observables (Hortúa et al., 2020; Wolz et al., 2023), and extract information from large-scale structure data using hybrid deep-learning methods (Ntampaka

et al., 2020). More broadly, simulation-based and likelihood-free inference methods have become an important part of the modern cosmological toolkit, particularly in settings where the likelihood is expensive or analytically inaccessible (Alsing et al., 2019; Cranmer et al., 2020; Cole et al., 2022; Surrao and Hill, 2024).

Despite their predictive success, many machine-learning approaches remain fundamentally black-box. In scientific applications, however, predictive accuracy alone is often insufficient; interpretability is also important for understanding how physical information is encoded in the data, as emphasized in recent work on interpretable and scientific machine learning (Molnar et al., 2020; Rowan and Doostan, 2025; Cuomo et al., 2022). This is particularly relevant in cosmology, where relationships between observables and parameters are physically structured and where interpretable approximations may help illuminate parameter sensitivities and degeneracies.

Symbolic regression provides a natural alternative. Rather than learning opaque internal representations, symbolic regression searches directly for analytic expressions relating inputs and outputs (Cranmer, 2023; Udrescu and Tegmark, 2020; Schmidt and Lipson, 2009; Makke and Chawla, 2024; Tenachi et al., 2023; Bartlett et al., 2025). Recent studies have high-

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lighted its potential for interpretable modeling and scientific discovery (Bartlett et al., 2024; Makke and Chawla, 2024; Tenachi et al., 2023; Bartlett et al., 2025). However, its application to cosmological parameter recovery from CMB observables remains relatively unexplored.

In this work, we investigate symbolic regression as an interpretable framework for recovering cosmological parameters from CMB power spectra. Our goal is not to replace full Bayesian inference pipelines, but rather to examine to what extent compact symbolic expressions can approximate the inverse mapping from TT , TE , and EE spectra to cosmological parameters within a controlled synthetic setting.

We focus on five parameters,

$$n_s, \ln(10^{10}A_s), \omega_b, \omega_{\text{cdm}}, \tau,$$

which span qualitatively different physical imprints on the CMB, including spectral tilt, overall amplitude scaling, baryon loading of the acoustic peaks, matter-density effects on peak morphology, and reionization-induced large-scale polarization signatures. This provides a useful testbed for assessing which parameter mappings are naturally compressible into compact symbolic forms and where physics-informed feature construction becomes necessary.

Our main results are as follows. Symbolic regression recovers n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ from synthetic CMB spectra with high fidelity while yielding compact analytic expressions. In contrast, ω_b is substantially more difficult to recover directly from raw spectra, but improves significantly once physically motivated acoustic peak-ratio features are introduced. Comparisons with Random Forest and multilayer perceptron (MLP) baselines further show that symbolic regression can remain competitive for several parameters while additionally providing explicit closed-form representations of the inferred mappings.

We additionally investigate robustness under controlled perturbations, bootstrap uncertainty estimation, and stability across random seeds and cross-validation folds in order to assess the reproducibility and reliability of the recovered symbolic relations.

This paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2 we describe the simulated dataset and preprocessing pipeline. In Sect. 3 we present the symbolic-regression framework, feature-engineering procedure, and baseline models. In Sect. 4 we present the main results, including robustness, interpretability, and uncertainty analyses. In Sect. 5 we discuss implications and limitations of the present approach, and we conclude in Sect. 6.

2. Dataset and physical setup

2.1. Parameter space

We construct a synthetic dataset of CMB power spectra by varying five cosmological parameters over ranges centered on

the Planck 2018 cosmology reported by Aghanim et al. (2020):

$$n_s \in [0.94, 1.00], \quad (1)$$

$$\ln(10^{10}A_s) \in [2.9, 3.2], \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_b \in [0.020, 0.024], \quad (3)$$

$$\omega_{\text{cdm}} \in [0.11, 0.14], \quad (4)$$

$$\tau \in [0.03, 0.08]. \quad (5)$$

Here, $\omega_b \equiv \Omega_b h^2$ and $\omega_{\text{cdm}} \equiv \Omega_{\text{cdm}} h^2$ denote the physical baryon and cold-dark-matter densities, respectively, consistent with the standard CAMB parameterization. The chosen intervals span realistic Λ CDM-like values while remaining broad enough to probe parameter dependence in the resulting spectra.

The Hubble parameter was fixed to

$$H_0 = 67.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1},$$

consistent with the Planck baseline cosmology reported by Aghanim et al. (2020). We therefore do not attempt full inference in the complete six-parameter Λ CDM space. Instead, we isolate a representative five-parameter subset in order to study the recoverability and interpretability of symbolic inverse mappings.

2.2. Sampling and CAMB spectrum generation

We sampled the five-dimensional parameter space using Latin hypercube sampling, which provides efficient coverage of multidimensional domains compared with naive random sampling. A total of 2000 cosmologies were generated using a fixed random seed of 42.

For each sampled point, we computed unlensed scalar CMB power spectra using CAMB, developed by Lewis et al. (2000). The primordial scalar amplitude supplied to CAMB was obtained from the sampled quantity $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$ as

$$A_s = \frac{\exp[\ln(10^{10}A_s)]}{10^{10}}.$$

We enabled scalar modes only, with tensor modes and lensing disabled. For each cosmology, we retained the TT , TE , and EE spectra over

$$\ell = 2, 3, \dots, 1001,$$

giving 1000 multipoles per spectrum. The three spectra were concatenated into a 3000-dimensional feature vector for each sample. All 2000 sampled cosmologies were successfully evaluated.

We use TT , TE , and EE jointly because they encode complementary cosmological information. The TT spectrum is sensitive to acoustic peak morphology and overall spectral shape, TE provides cross-correlation information, and EE is especially informative for parameters such as τ , whose signature is strongest in large-scale polarization.

2.3. Preprocessing and feature representations

The dataset was split into training and test sets using an 80/20 split with `random_state=42`. Input features were standardized with a z-score transformation using `StandardScaler`, fitted on the training set and then applied to the test set to avoid information leakage. Symbolic regression was therefore performed on standardized spectral coefficients. For readability, we refer to input variables using their spectral labels, but the learned expressions are formally functions of affine-rescaled variables of the form $(X - \mu)/\sigma$.

In addition to the raw concatenated spectra, we constructed a physics-informed feature representation for the ω_b analysis. This was motivated by baryon loading, which modifies the relative heights of acoustic peaks in the TT spectrum, as discussed for example by Page et al. (2003), Corasaniti and Melchiorri (2008), and Bond et al. (2003). We estimated band-averaged amplitudes near the first three acoustic peaks and constructed compact summary features from their amplitudes and ratios. Additional engineered combinations, including odd-even peak contrasts and a simple peak-curvature feature, were tested but did not improve test-set performance and were not retained in the final analysis.

2.4. Scope of the dataset

The base dataset used throughout this work is fully synthetic and deterministic. It does not include instrumental noise, foreground contamination, beam effects, masking, lensing, or likelihood-level observational modeling. The purpose of this work is therefore not to compete directly with full observational CMB inference pipelines, but to test whether symbolic regression can recover accurate and physically interpretable inverse mappings from idealized theoretical spectra in a controlled setting.

In later robustness analyses, we additionally consider controlled perturbations applied to the standardized spectral coefficients in order to assess the stability of the recovered symbolic relations under moderate input variations. These perturbations are intended only as simplified robustness tests and should not be interpreted as realistic observational noise models.

3. Methods

3.1. Symbolic regression with PySR

We used PySR, introduced by Cranmer (2023), as the primary symbolic-regression framework. PySR searches for analytic expressions using an evolutionary algorithm that balances predictive accuracy against expression complexity, making it well suited to scientific settings where compact and interpretable formulas are preferred over highly flexible but opaque models.

Initial experiments employed a broad operator set including arithmetic operations, logarithms, exponentials, square roots, and trigonometric functions. Although these runs often achieved high predictive accuracy, many resulting expressions were unnecessarily complex and difficult to interpret physically.

We therefore performed additional runs using a restricted operator set,

$$\{+, -, \times, /, \log, \sqrt{\quad}\},$$

which substantially improved interpretability while preserving strong predictive performance for several parameters.

Model selection was based on the symbolic-regression objective implemented in PySR together with practical considerations of simplicity, stability, and qualitative physical plausibility.

All reported symbolic expressions were evaluated across the full sampled feature domain used in training and testing and were verified to produce finite real-valued predictions without invalid logarithmic, square-root, or division operations. Expressions exhibiting unstable or invalid evaluations under perturbation tests were excluded from the reported analysis.

3.2. Parameter-wise regression

Separate symbolic-regression models were trained for each target parameter,

$$n_s, \ln(10^{10}A_s), \omega_b, \omega_{\text{cdm}}, \tau.$$

This parameter-wise approach improves interpretability by allowing direct examination of which spectral regions and combinations of observables are most relevant to each parameter, while avoiding additional complexity associated with a joint multivariate fit.

3.3. Physics-informed feature engineering for ω_b

Among the five parameters considered, ω_b proved the most difficult to recover from raw spectra alone. This is physically expected because baryon density is encoded primarily through acoustic peak morphology, particularly the relative enhancement of compression and rarefaction peaks caused by baryon loading, as discussed by Page et al. (2003), Corasaniti and Melchiorri (2008), and Bond et al. (2003).

Motivated by this, we constructed engineered features based on approximate acoustic peak amplitudes in the TT spectrum. We selected three fixed multipole regions near the first three acoustic peaks ($\ell \approx 220, 540, 800$) and estimated their amplitudes using band-averaged windows of width $\Delta\ell = 5$. No smoothing, interpolation, or explicit peak-finding procedure was applied. Instead, these fixed-window averages provide a simple and reproducible proxy for peak amplitudes.

From these quantities, we constructed compact peak-ratio features designed to capture baryon-sensitive acoustic structure. Symbolic regression on these engineered features yielded substantially more compact and accurate models for ω_b than regression performed directly on the raw spectra.

3.4. Baseline models

To benchmark predictive performance, we trained Random Forest regressors on the same standardized spectral inputs and train-test splits as the symbolic-regression models. The Random Forest baseline used 500 trees, unrestricted tree depth, and a fixed random seed of 42.

In addition, we trained a multilayer perceptron (MLP) baseline on the same standardized spectral inputs and train–test splits. The MLP consisted of three fully connected hidden layers with sizes 256, 128, and 64, ReLU activations, and was optimized using Adam with mean-squared-error loss. We used a batch size of 64, an initial learning rate of 10^{-3} , L_2 regularization with $\alpha = 10^{-4}$, early stopping, and a maximum of 1000 training iterations. The target variable was standardized using a `TransformedTargetRegressor`.

The goal of these comparisons is not to demonstrate that symbolic regression universally outperforms higher-capacity models, but rather to assess the tradeoff between predictive flexibility and analytic interpretability.

3.5. Evaluation metrics

We evaluated model performance using the coefficient of determination R^2 and the mean absolute error (MAE). For targets y and predictions \hat{y} ,

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i |y_i - \hat{y}_i|. \quad (7)$$

Because the dataset is deterministic and noise-free, high R^2 values are expected when the inverse mapping from spectra to parameters is successfully captured. However, near-unity R^2 values should not be interpreted as guarantees of generalization beyond the sampled parameter domain.

All symbolic-regression experiments were evaluated across ten independent random seeds and five cross-validation folds. The reported symbolic expressions correspond to representative Pareto-optimal models selected based on predictive performance, expression simplicity, and qualitative stability across random seeds and cross-validation folds. Summary statistics for the seed and cross-validation experiments are reported in Appendix B.

3.6. Noise robustness experiments

To assess robustness under controlled perturbations, we injected additive Gaussian noise into the standardized spectral coefficients. For an input feature vector x , the perturbed features were constructed as

$$x' = x + \sigma_n \epsilon,$$

where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ independently for each feature and σ_n denotes the noise amplitude. The perturbations were applied independently to each standardized spectral coefficient and correspond to additive Gaussian noise in feature space rather than to a physically calibrated observational noise model.

We considered both:

1. models trained on clean spectra and evaluated on noisy spectra;
2. models trained and evaluated on noisy spectra.

We considered noise amplitudes

$$\sigma_n \in \{0.5, 1.0, 2.0\},$$

applied uniformly across the standardized TT , TE , and EE spectral coefficients. These experiments are intended only as controlled robustness tests and should not be interpreted as realistic observational noise modeling or as substitutes for full experimental likelihood analyses.

The perturbation experiments were designed to probe the stability of the learned symbolic mappings under controlled feature-space distortions rather than to reproduce a physically complete observational covariance model for CMB measurements.

3.7. Bootstrap uncertainty estimation

Predictive uncertainty was estimated using bootstrap ensembles of symbolic-regression models. For each target parameter, we generated

$$N_{\text{boot}} = 20$$

bootstrap-resampled training sets and trained independent symbolic-regression models on each realization. This ensemble size was chosen as a computationally tractable diagnostic of predictive uncertainty rather than as a complete uncertainty-calibration study.

For a given input spectrum x , the bootstrap predictive mean was computed as

$$\mu(x) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{boot}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{boot}}} f_k(x),$$

where $f_k(x)$ denotes the prediction from the k -th bootstrap model.

The predictive variance was estimated as

$$\sigma^2(x) = \frac{1}{N_{\text{boot}} - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{boot}}} [f_k(x) - \mu(x)]^2.$$

We evaluated empirical coverage by measuring the fraction of test samples whose true values fell within the bootstrap uncertainty intervals. Calibration diagnostics were assessed by comparing bootstrap predictive uncertainty against the realized absolute prediction error across the test set.

3.8. Computational considerations

All symbolic-regression experiments were performed using PySR on CPU-based hardware. The restricted symbolic-regression runs were substantially more computationally efficient than the broader operator searches while yielding comparable predictive performance. Random Forest and MLP baselines trained significantly faster than the symbolic-regression models, reflecting the higher optimization cost associated with evolutionary symbolic search.

The computational expense of symbolic regression was dominated by repeated expression evaluation and Pareto-front exploration across candidate symbolic forms. However, once trained, the resulting symbolic models provide extremely lightweight analytic surrogate relations with negligible inference cost.

4. Results

We now present the performance of symbolic regression across the five cosmological parameters considered in this work. We focus on predictive accuracy, interpretability, robustness, and the extent to which different parameter mappings admit compact symbolic representations.

4.1. Overall performance

Table 1 summarizes the predictive performance of symbolic regression, Random Forest, and multilayer perceptron baselines. Symbolic regression achieves high accuracy for n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ , with R^2 values close to unity. In particular, the symbolic models for n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, and τ achieve performance broadly comparable to the Random Forest and MLP baselines while retaining compact analytic structure. Stability tests across ten random seeds and five cross-validation folds are reported in Appendix Appendix B; the restricted symbolic-regression models retain high predictive accuracy with only modest scatter across both tests.

The values reported in Table 1 correspond to representative symbolic-regression realizations, while Appendix Appendix B reports stability statistics across ten random seeds and five cross-validation folds.

The strongest discrepancy occurs for ω_b . Symbolic regression trained directly on raw spectra reaches only $R^2 = 0.6107$, whereas the Random Forest baseline achieves $R^2 = 0.9981$. This indicates that the information required to infer ω_b is present in the spectra but is not easily compressible into low-complexity symbolic forms. Introducing physics-informed acoustic peak-ratio features substantially improves symbolic-regression performance to $R^2 = 0.8016$, although a significant gap relative to the higher-capacity baseline remains.

Overall, the results suggest a parameter-dependent pattern in symbolic recoverability. Some cosmological parameters admit compact analytic approximations with very high predictive accuracy, whereas others require either more expressive models or physics-informed feature representations. This behavior is summarized in Fig. 1.

4.2. Feature and operator ablations

To investigate how cosmological information is distributed across the spectra, we performed feature-ablation experiments using different combinations of TT , TE , and EE inputs. The results are shown in Fig. 2.

The feature-ablation analysis reveals clear parameter-dependent behavior. Parameters such as n_s and $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$ remain recoverable from reduced feature sets, whereas τ depends strongly on polarization information, particularly EE . The combined $TT + TE + EE$ representation consistently provides the best overall performance, indicating that the different spectra contain complementary cosmological information.

We also explored the role of symbolic-search complexity through operator ablations. Figure 3 compares symbolic-regression performance for three operator configurations: linear-only, restricted symbolic operators, and a broader nonlinear operator set.

Figure 1: **Model comparison across cosmological parameters.** Unexplained variance ($1 - R^2$) for symbolic regression, Random Forest, and MLP models across the five cosmological parameters considered in this work. Lower values correspond to better predictive performance. Symbolic regression performs competitively for n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ , while ω_b remains substantially more difficult to recover from raw spectra alone. The MLP baseline generally performs competitively with the ensemble-based models, although it does not provide explicit analytic representations of the recovered parameter mappings.

Linear-only models perform substantially worse for all parameters, indicating that the inverse mappings are intrinsically nonlinear. However, the restricted symbolic operator set achieves performance comparable to the full search space while producing substantially simpler expressions. This suggests that much of the recoverable structure in the present setting can be represented using relatively low-complexity symbolic forms.

4.3. Physical interpretability of recovered expressions

For n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ , symbolic regression identifies compact analytic structures with strong predictive performance. The complete expressions are provided in Appendix A, while here we focus on their broader physical interpretation.

The recovered expression for n_s primarily combines low- and high- ℓ polarization structure together with smaller contributions from high- ℓ temperature information, consistent with the sensitivity of the scalar spectral tilt to scale-dependent anisotropy patterns. For $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, the symbolic model is dominated by high- ℓ temperature information with subleading polarization corrections, reflecting the role of A_s as an overall amplitude parameter. The symbolic model for ω_{cdm} combines intermediate- and high- ℓ temperature and cross-correlation structure, consistent with the influence of matter density on acoustic peak morphology and small-scale power. Finally, the recovered expression for τ depends explicitly on low- ℓ polarization information, in agreement with the expected imprint of reionization on large-scale EE modes.

Because neighboring multipoles are strongly correlated, the precise identity of individual selected ℓ -modes should not be overinterpreted. More robustly, the symbolic expressions should be understood as compact representations of broader angular-scale structure and cross-spectrum relationships.

To further probe interpretability, we performed localized perturbation tests in which specific spectral regions were selectively perturbed during inference. Figure 4 summarizes the resulting degradation in predictive performance.

Table 1: Performance of symbolic regression (SR), Random Forest (RF), and multilayer perceptron (MLP) models for the cosmological parameters considered in this work. For ω_b , we report both the raw-spectra symbolic-regression result and the feature-engineered peak-ratio result.

Parameter	SR R^2	SR MAE	RF R^2	RF MAE	MLP R^2	MLP MAE
n_s	0.9977	0.000654	0.9683	0.002510	0.9943	0.001050
$\ln(10^{10}A_s)$	0.9989	0.001509	0.9957	0.004351	0.9980	0.002957
ω_b raw	0.6107	0.000603	0.9981	0.000037	0.9976	0.000039
ω_b peak ratios	0.8016	0.000437	—	—	—	—
ω_{cdm}	0.9953	0.000440	0.9991	0.000196	0.9947	0.000516
τ	0.9984	0.000458	0.9965	0.000669	0.9935	0.000861

Figure 2: **Feature-ablation analysis across CMB spectra.** Predictive performance for symbolic regression under different spectral feature combinations. The results demonstrate that different cosmological parameters depend on distinct combinations of temperature and polarization information, with the joint $TT + TE + EE$ representation consistently yielding the strongest overall performance.

The perturbation analysis recovers physically expected sensitivities. In particular, τ shows strong dependence on low- ℓ polarization information, while n_s is most sensitive to higher- ℓ structure. These results support the interpretation that the symbolic models are capturing physically meaningful spectral sensitivities rather than relying solely on arbitrary correlations within the sampled dataset.

Across independent symbolic-regression runs, the exact analytic forms varied moderately due to the stochastic nature of the symbolic search. However, the dominant spectral regions and operator structures remained qualitatively stable for the highest-performing parameters. In particular, repeated runs consistently selected combinations of high- ℓ temperature information for n_s and $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, low- ℓ polarization information for τ , and mixed $TT-TE$ structure for ω_{cdm} . This suggests that the recovered symbolic relations capture stable spectral sensitivities rather than arbitrary symbolic combinations tied to a single optimization realization.

4.4. Controlled perturbation robustness and uncertainty analysis

To assess robustness, we evaluated symbolic-regression performance under increasing levels of controlled Gaussian perturbations. Figure 5 compares models trained on clean spectra

Figure 3: **Operator-set ablation for symbolic regression.** Predictive performance under different symbolic operator configurations. Linear-only models perform substantially worse, while the restricted symbolic operator set achieves nearly the same accuracy as the larger nonlinear search space with significantly improved interpretability.

with models trained using noisy augmentations.

Models trained exclusively on clean spectra degrade rapidly as perturbation amplitudes increase, whereas models trained with perturbation augmentation remain substantially more stable. This indicates that symbolic regression can retain substantial predictive fidelity under moderate perturbation levels when robustness is incorporated during training.

We additionally estimated predictive uncertainty using bootstrap resampling. Figure 6 shows the empirical coverage of the resulting uncertainty intervals.

The bootstrap intervals generally achieve near-nominal two- σ coverage, although calibration quality varies across parameters. The strongest uncertainty–error alignment is observed for parameters such as n_s , while more structurally complex mappings exhibit weaker uncertainty–error alignment. Additional uncertainty diagnostics are presented in Appendix B.

4.5. The challenge of ω_b

Among the five parameters considered, ω_b represents the most challenging case for compact symbolic recovery from raw spectra. This behavior is physically plausible because baryon density primarily affects the relative structure of acoustic peaks rather than inducing a smooth global spectral response.

To better expose this information, we introduced engineered acoustic peak-ratio features derived from fixed-window averages near the first few TT acoustic peaks. Figure 7 summarizes the resulting improvement.

The recovered symbolic form is remarkably simple,

$$\omega_b \propto \frac{p_1}{p_2},$$

Figure 4: **Perturbation-based interpretability analysis.** Larger values indicate stronger sensitivity to perturbations within the corresponding spectral region. The results recover physically expected parameter sensitivities, including strong low- ℓ polarization dependence for τ and enhanced high- ℓ sensitivity for n_s .

where p_1 and p_2 denote band-averaged amplitudes near the first two acoustic peaks. This structure is qualitatively consistent with the expected role of baryon loading in modulating relative peak heights.

Although the engineered representation substantially improves symbolic-regression performance, a large gap relative to the Random Forest baseline remains. This suggests that the full mapping from spectra to ω_b contains additional distributed structure that is not fully captured by low-complexity symbolic expressions.

Overall, the ω_b analysis highlights the importance of feature representation in interpretable symbolic modeling. The recoverability of physically meaningful relationships depends not only on model expressivity, but also on how relevant physical structure is encoded in the input features.

5. Discussion

Our results show that symbolic regression can recover several cosmological parameters from CMB power spectra with high predictive accuracy in a controlled synthetic setting while providing compact analytic representations of the inferred mappings. The effectiveness of the method is strongly parameter-dependent and reflects both the physical encoding of information in the spectra and the choice of input representation. Fixing H_0 and using unlensed scalar spectra simplifies the inverse problem relative to full observational inference by removing geometric degeneracies, lensing-induced mode coupling, and instrumental or astrophysical systematics.

For n_s , $\ln(10^{10} A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ , the inverse mappings appear sufficiently compressible that symbolic regression identifies low-complexity analytic approximations directly from the spectra. These mappings are either relatively smooth over the sampled parameter domain or tied to distinctive spectral regions, such as the low- ℓ polarization dependence of τ . In contrast, ω_b is more difficult to recover from raw spectra because its imprint is encoded through structured acoustic peak morphology. The improvement obtained from acoustic peak-ratio fea-

Figure 5: **Robustness under controlled spectral perturbations.** Predictive performance as a function of perturbation amplitude applied to the standardized spectral coefficients. Models trained only on clean spectra degrade rapidly under increasing perturbation levels, whereas models trained with perturbation augmentation retain substantially improved stability and predictive fidelity.

tures illustrates that domain-informed feature construction can substantially improve both predictive performance and symbolic compactness.

These results should not be interpreted as establishing a strict hierarchy among cosmological parameters. Rather, they indicate a parameter-dependent pattern of symbolic recoverability in the present setup. Parameters associated with broad spectral trends or approximate global amplitude rescaling are more readily approximated by compact symbolic forms, whereas parameters whose signatures depend on structured contrasts or distributed spectral information are more challenging for low-complexity symbolic models. The behavior of ω_{cdm} lies between these regimes: it is recovered accurately, but with a somewhat more structured dependence on TT and TE information.

The interpretability of the recovered expressions should also be understood with care. Because the models are trained on standardized inputs and neighboring multipoles are strongly correlated, individual selected multipoles should not be assigned unique physical significance. The more robust interpretation is that the expressions encode broader angular-scale structure and cross-spectrum combinations. This interpretation is supported by the feature-ablation and perturbation analyses, which recover physically plausible sensitivities such as the importance of low- ℓ EE information for τ and high- ℓ structure for n_s .

The robustness and uncertainty analyses further clarify the scope of the results. Models trained only on clean spectra degrade under injected noise, whereas noise-augmented training improves stability. Bootstrap intervals provide broadly reasonable empirical coverage, though calibration quality varies across parameters. These findings suggest that symbolic regression can be made more robust, but also that uncertainty

Figure 6: **Bootstrap uncertainty coverage.** Empirical two- σ coverage for bootstrap-derived predictive uncertainties across the five cosmological parameters. The dashed line indicates the nominal 95% reference level. Coverage values near the dashed reference line correspond to approximately calibrated uncertainty intervals.

Figure 7: **Physics-informed feature engineering for ω_b .** Comparison between symbolic regression trained on raw spectra and on acoustic peak-ratio features. Physics-informed feature construction substantially improves both predictive accuracy and compactness of the resulting symbolic expressions.

calibration and noise modeling are essential for moving beyond idealized spectra.

Several limitations remain. The dataset is synthetic and does not include foregrounds, beam effects, masking, lensing, instrumental noise, or a full likelihood model. The analysis treats each parameter independently rather than performing joint inference in the full cosmological parameter space. The baseline models are intended as reference comparisons rather than exhaustively optimized predictors. Finally, while we include robustness and uncertainty diagnostics, a complete assessment would require broader tests over sampling strategy, noise models, operator sets, and feature representations.

Future work should extend this framework to more realistic observational settings, including lensed spectra, experimental noise, foreground residuals, and partial-sky effects. Joint symbolic modeling of multiple parameters would also be valuable for studying degeneracies and assessing whether compact analytic forms can capture coupled parameter dependencies. More broadly, symbolic regression may be useful as an interpretable component within simulation-based or likelihood-free cosmological inference pipelines, where compact surrogate relations can complement high-capacity predictive models.

6. Conclusions

We have investigated symbolic regression as a framework for recovering cosmological parameters from CMB power spectra. Using synthetic TT , TE , and EE spectra generated with CAMB, we trained symbolic models to recover five cosmological parameters:

$$n_s, \ln(10^{10}A_s), \omega_b, \omega_{\text{cdm}}, \tau.$$

Our main findings are as follows.

1. Symbolic regression recovers n_s , $\ln(10^{10}A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ with high predictive accuracy within the sampled parameter domain while yielding compact analytic expressions. These parameters appear comparatively more compressible, in the sense that low-complexity symbolic forms can approximate the inverse mapping from spectra to parameters with predictive performance comparable to the higher-capacity baseline models.
2. The baryon density ω_b is substantially more difficult to recover directly from raw spectra. Introducing physics-informed acoustic peak-ratio features improves both predictive accuracy and symbolic compactness, indicating that feature representation plays an important role in interpretable symbolic modeling.
3. Feature-ablation and perturbation analyses recover physically plausible parameter sensitivities, including the importance of low- ℓ polarization information for τ and higher- ℓ structure for n_s . These results support the interpretation that the symbolic models capture physically plausible spectral sensitivities rather than relying solely on arbitrary correlations within the sampled dataset.
4. Comparison with Random Forest and MLP baselines highlights a parameter-dependent tradeoff between predictive flexibility and analytic interpretability. Higher-capacity models more effectively capture distributed or structurally complex dependencies, whereas symbolic regression provides explicit closed-form representations that expose broad angular-scale and cross-spectrum structure.
5. Robustness and bootstrap analyses indicate that symbolic regression can retain predictive fidelity under moderate controlled perturbations when trained appropriately, although uncertainty calibration quality varies across parameters and remains an important area for further investigation.

Taken together, these results support symbolic regression as a complementary interpretable surrogate-modeling approach for controlled cosmological inference problems rather than as a replacement for high-capacity inference methods. Its primary strength lies in identifying compact analytic approximations to otherwise high-dimensional inverse mappings that expose relationships between cosmological parameters and physically meaningful spectral structure.

At the same time, the interpretability of the recovered expressions should be understood in context. Because the models are trained on standardized inputs and neighboring multipoles are

strongly correlated, the symbolic expressions are most robustly interpreted at the level of broader angular-scale structure rather than as exact statements about individual multipoles.

Future work should extend this framework to more realistic observational settings including lensing, instrumental noise, foreground contamination, masking, and joint parameter inference. It would also be valuable to investigate the stability of the recovered symbolic relations under alternative feature representations, sampling strategies, and symbolic search configurations. More broadly, symbolic regression may provide a useful interpretable component within simulation-based and likelihood-free cosmological inference frameworks, particularly in settings where compact analytic surrogates can complement high-capacity predictive models.

Data availability

The data used in this study are synthetic CMB power spectra generated using the CAMB Boltzmann code. The datasets, trained models, and analysis code are publicly available at Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20224914>. The data can be reproduced using the parameter ranges and methodology described in Secs. 2 and 3. This repository includes all scripts required to regenerate the synthetic datasets and reproduce the symbolic regression results presented in this work.

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Appendix A. Full symbolic expressions

In this appendix we provide the complete symbolic expressions recovered by the restricted symbolic-regression models. These expressions correspond to representative models selected from the symbolic-regression Pareto fronts according to predictive performance, expression simplicity, and qualitative stability within the sampled parameter domain.

All symbolic regression was performed on standardized spectral coefficients. For readability, we express the recovered relations using the corresponding spectral labels (TT_ℓ , TE_ℓ , and EE_ℓ). Because neighboring multipoles are strongly correlated, the precise identity of individual selected multipoles should not be overinterpreted; the expressions are more robustly understood as compact representations of broader angular-scale structure.

Appendix A.1. Scalar Spectral Index (n_s)

$$n_s = (0.0033236402 EE_{\ell=73} - 0.037307825) \times \left[(EE_{\ell=53} - EE_{\ell=454}) + (EE_{\ell=431} - TT_{\ell=750}) \right] + 0.96965224 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Appendix A.2. Scalar Amplitude ($\ln(10^{10}A_s)$)

$$\ln(10^{10}A_s) = \log \left(TT_{\ell=812} + TT_{\ell=754} - 0.20393687(TE_{\ell=6} + TE_{\ell=570} + TE_{\ell=8}) + TE_{\ell=5} + 21.183264 \right) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Appendix A.3. Cold Dark Matter Density (ω_{cdm})

$$\omega_{\text{cdm}} = 0.011663058 TE_{\ell=840} + 0.00084133167(TE_{\ell=296} + 3.6445718) \times (TT_{\ell=930} + TE_{\ell=725} + 0.8987217) + 0.12191176 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

All reported symbolic expressions were evaluated over the full test domain and verified to produce finite real-valued predictions. During perturbation tests, invalid symbolic evaluations were monitored and found to be negligible within the sampled parameter range.

Appendix A.4. Optical Depth (τ)

$$\tau = 0.014767303 + \left[0.0017324582(TT_{\ell=788} + TE_{\ell=393}) + 2.1543493 TE_{\ell=108} \right] + 0.033914566 \times \sqrt{EE_{\ell=8} + 1.5720251} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Appendix A.5. Baryon Density (ω_b)

For the feature-engineered ω_b analysis, symbolic regression recovered the compact relation

$$\omega_b = 0.0010301905 \frac{p_1}{p_2} + 0.022005528, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where p_1 and p_2 denote fixed-window band-averaged TT amplitudes centered near the first and second acoustic peaks, respectively.

Appendix B. Stability across seeds and cross-validation

Table B.2 reports the stability of the restricted symbolic-regression models across ten random seeds and five cross-validation folds. The results show that the high-performing symbolic-regression models remain stable across both random-seed variation and cross-validation folds, indicating that the reported performance trends are not artifacts of a single symbolic-regression realization, random initialization, or train–test split.

For clarity, stability statistics are reported only for the restricted symbolic-regression models achieving consistently high predictive performance; the feature-engineered ω_b analysis is discussed separately in Sect. 4.

Table B.2: Stability of restricted symbolic-regression models across random seeds and cross-validation folds. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

Parameter	Seed R^2	Seed MAE	CV R^2	CV MAE
n_s	0.9928 ± 0.0041	$(1.12 \pm 0.32) \times 10^{-3}$	0.9869 ± 0.0083	$(1.49 \pm 0.48) \times 10^{-3}$
$\ln(10^{10} A_s)$	0.9974 ± 0.0013	$(3.39 \pm 0.85) \times 10^{-3}$	0.9975 ± 0.0015	$(3.30 \pm 1.18) \times 10^{-3}$
ω_{cdm}	0.9980 ± 0.0008	$(2.96 \pm 0.75) \times 10^{-4}$	0.9973 ± 0.0018	$(3.58 \pm 1.10) \times 10^{-4}$
τ	0.9962 ± 0.0028	$(6.70 \pm 2.48) \times 10^{-4}$	0.9931 ± 0.0065	$(8.21 \pm 4.24) \times 10^{-4}$

Appendix C. Bootstrap prediction diagnostics

Figure C.8 shows predicted-versus-true comparisons for the bootstrap symbolic-regression ensembles. Shaded regions denote the corresponding bootstrap uncertainty intervals.

The bootstrap ensembles reproduce the dominant trends observed in the main analysis, although uncertainty intervals broaden for parameters with more structurally complex symbolic mappings. The strongest agreement is observed for n_s and $\ln(10^{10} A_s)$, which exhibit relatively stable symbolic recoverability across bootstrap realizations.

Appendix D. Uncertainty calibration diagnostics

Figure D.9 shows uncertainty calibration diagnostics comparing bootstrap predictive uncertainties against absolute prediction errors.

The calibration diagnostics indicate that bootstrap-derived uncertainty estimates track realized prediction errors qualitatively, although the uncertainty–error alignment weakens for parameters with more distributed spectral dependencies.

Appendix E. Complexity–loss frontiers

Figure E.10 shows the symbolic-regression complexity–loss frontiers for the restricted symbolic models.

The complexity–loss frontiers show that predictive improvements saturate beyond moderate symbolic complexity, supporting the use of restricted operator sets for obtaining more interpretable symbolic relations without substantial performance degradation.

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Figure C.8: **Bootstrap predicted-versus-true comparisons.** Predicted and true parameter values for the bootstrap symbolic-regression ensembles. Shaded regions indicate the estimated bootstrap uncertainty intervals. The models recover n_s , $\ln(10^{10} A_s)$, ω_{cdm} , and τ with high fidelity over the sampled parameter domain.

Figure D.9: **Bootstrap uncertainty calibration diagnostics.** Absolute prediction error as a function of bootstrap-derived predictive uncertainty for the recovered cosmological parameters. The Spearman correlation coefficient shown in each panel quantifies the alignment between predicted uncertainty and realized error. Stronger monotonic trends indicate better alignment between predicted uncertainty and realized prediction error.

★ Selected expression

Figure E.10: **Complexity–loss frontiers for symbolic regression.** Tradeoff between symbolic expression complexity and regression loss for the restricted symbolic-regression models. Performance improvements saturate beyond moderate symbolic complexity, indicating diminishing returns from increasingly complicated expressions. Lower loss values correspond to improved predictive performance.